

Experiencing open practices – a qualitative long-term study among early career educational researchers

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ABSTRACT

Keywords

Open research practices, qualitative study, educational research

Purpose of this paper

The long-term study aims at getting deeper insights in how early career researchers adopt open practices in their daily work, i.e. research and teaching. Quantitative surveys show that researchers think differently about open practices (Levin & Leonelli, 2017; Levin, Leonelli, Weckowska, Castle, & Dupré, 2016), have attitudes against data sharing (Ünal, Chowdhury, Kurbanoglu, Boustany, & Walton, 2019) and are influenced by diverse factors like communities and policies (Bossu & Stagg, 2018; Kim & Nah, 2018; Linek, Fecher, Friesike, & Hebing, 2017). The current study offers researchers to test open practices and reflect on them during their active daily work. The focus lies on practices that relate to aspects of open science (Kramer & Bosman, 2017) and open education (Cronin, 2017). The study contributes to a better understanding on how personal-, social- and environmental-dependent factors influence the adaptation of open practices in research and education. The approach is user-centric, i.e. participants choose their own practices to test and reflect on them for about half a year.

The study focuses on two main research questions:

- Which factors influence research practices?
- In which way are those factors dependent from each other?

Design/methodology/approach

The long-term study started in April 2019 with five educational researchers. In a workshop, participants learned about the ideas of open science and education (Table 1) and were able to test several tools to be applied in their research or teaching. At the end of the workshop, participants wrote up scenarios (Table 2) in which they would like to apply open practices for the next months. Currently, they are reflecting on their experiences via diary entries, i.e. text or audio they send to us.

A second phase in September started with four new participants. In April 2020, all participants will join a workshop to share experiences and reflect on drawbacks and best practices to apply open scenarios.

Expected Findings

The workshop data analysis gives first insights into the experiences of our participants regarding open science topics (Table 1). Those topics were discussed within the workshop and participants got shown examples on how to apply those practices with exemplary tools and services. We summarized workshop discussions in an online editor pad and a Wikiversity website¹. We are currently analyzing interview data and first diary entries and will discuss first at the symposium (Table 2). With the interviews, we get deeper insights into the researcher's past and current work and environment, their attitudes towards roles and tasks in research and teaching and their experience with practicing openness. With the diaries, we expect to see a reflection on the open scenarios tested in relation to influencing internal and external factors.

Table 1. Number of participant answers (multiple choice) at workshop in April, asking about experience with open science aspects.

	I heard of that	I have own experience with that	I'd like to know about that
Open Access	3	3	2
Open Data	3	1	4
Open Source	1	3	4
Open Peer Review	1	-	5
Open Methodology	-	1	5
Open Educational Resources	3	4	2
Citizen Science	3	1	1

¹ <https://de.wikiversity.org/wiki/OPER>

Open educational practices	3	-	5
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Table 2. Participants, their scenarios and first experiences.

Participant	Scenario	Diary entries
<p>Participant 1</p> <p>Background: 2013-2019 PhD in education</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of Cryptpad for teaching in a seminar for language advancement in primary schools - Goals: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Encouraging collaboration among the students - Training of the articulateness of the students 	<p>Three entries:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Limited applicability of Cryptpad due to little usage of laptops by students - Feedback from 19 students at the end of the seminar: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Some found it practical, others confusing to use - Participant's conclusion: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - For optimal utilization of Cryptpad further training of students is needed
<p>Participant 2</p> <p>Background: 2012-2018 PhD in engineering mathematics</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of Cryptpad for collaboration with colleagues for project for evaluation of the study program - Goal: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transparency of the workflow 	<p>Three entries:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - At first reluctance of colleagues - Pros: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Location-independency for collaborative work - Easy change from Excel - Cons: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Lack of user friendliness - Error reports undermining of the acceptance of Cryptpad
<p>Participant 3</p> <p>Background: 2011-2016 PhD in education</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scenario 1: Use of Cryptpad for collaboration with colleagues - Goal: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Higher efficiency of collaborative work 	<p>Two entries</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pros: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transparent workflow - Easy to access and to use - Easy storage of different pads in drive (folders) - High acceptance among colleagues - Cons: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - None so far
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Scenario 2: Use of Zotero for the organization of literature - Goal: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Independence from Citavi 	<p>One entry:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pros: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Open Source = costless - Easy to use - Works faster than Citavi - Cons: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Less clarity in comparison to Citavi
<p>Participant 4</p> <p>Background : 2019 start with doctorate in education <i>Has left the OPER-study due to other work duties</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Use of the platform OPAL in a seminar - Goal: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promoting collaboration among students 	<p>One entry:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pros: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Platform is already known among students - Cons: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Disappearance of uploaded materials

		- Constant system changes of the platform > undermining of usability
Participant 5 Background: 2016-2018 PhD in chemistry education	- Scenario 1: Use of OLAT in a seminar - Goal: - Better collaboration among students	No entry so far
	- Scenario 2: Use of Zenodo and Impactstory - Goal: - Enhancement of the participant's outreach	No entry so far
Participant 6 Background: 2018 Start with doctorate in Education	- Scenario 1: Use of Hypothes.is in a seminar - Goal: common annotation of texts with students	No entry so far
	- Scenario 2: Upload of own teaching materials in ZOERR	No entry so far

Research limitations

The qualitative study gives deeper insights, but is not representative for early career educational researchers. Researchers, who were willing to participate, had already heard of open science or open access and are highly interested to learn about it. We would not find researcher, who are rather reluctant towards open practices or have good reasons not to apply them. Moreover, one participant opted out because their work tasks changed and they could not apply educational scenario intended.

Practical implications

The findings from researchers' practical experience will allow actors to better understand scientists' needs while practicing openness. This informs providers of research infrastructures and services, policy makers and heads of research institutes and will help them to improve their support for early career researchers.

What is original of paper

To our best knowledge, the study is one of the first approaches to accompany early career researchers on their way to apply open practices in their actual working environment during a

long-term phase. Results will reflect on the success and drawbacks in practicing openness in time and in real-life spaces.

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